

Undocumented Emigration: Evidence from Mozambican Workers on South African Farms

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Resumo:

Esta pesquisa tem como objectivo abordar as especificidades do trabalho migratório, bem como as práticas e experiências vividas pelos trabalhadores moçambicanos em explorações agrícolas na África do Sul. Trata-se de uma perspectiva que procura analisar e compreender as condições legais em que esses trabalhadores emigram, a natureza dos seus contratos de trabalho, as condições em que exercem as suas actividades laborais e a possibilidade de enviarem remessas às suas famílias em Moçambique. A pesquisa baseou-se numa abordagem qualitativa e, por meio de entrevistas semi-estruturadas, foi seleccionada uma amostra de 15 trabalhadores agrícolas moçambicanos, de modo a permitir uma compreensão aprofundada das suas representações sociais, das suas experiências vividas nas explorações agrícolas e do seu quotidiano. Os principais resultados revelaram que as razões mais relevantes para a migração foram a pobreza, a falta de oportunidades de emprego, conflitos familiares, a sobrelotação das habitações, a escassez de alimentos causada pela irregularidade das chuvas e pelas secas, bem como a influência de amigos e pares que já haviam migrado. Verificou-se igualmente que agricultores individuais e/ou empresas agrícolas recorrem deliberadamente a procedimentos administrativos informais para tirar proveito de migrantes desprotegidos e em situação irregular, os quais não dispõem de recursos para contratar advogados que defendam os seus direitos ou para procurar apoio fora dos seus próprios círculos sociais. Mais importante ainda, os resultados demonstram que, embora esses trabalhadores enfrentem inúmeras dificuldades durante o trabalho nas explorações agrícolas, os rendimentos obtidos permitem melhorias significativas nas suas condições de vida. Entre essas melhorias destacam-se a aquisição de parcelas de terra onde constroem habitações mais resistentes e equipadas com diversos serviços e comodidades, bem

como a criação de bancas e pequenos negócios. Tais iniciativas contribuem para reduzir os efeitos da pobreza e promover uma melhor qualidade de vida e bem-estar dos seus familiares.

Palavras-Chave: Emigração indocumentada, Trabalhadores agrícolas moçambicanos, Experiência vivida, Travessia de fronteiras, Remessas.

Abstract:

This research aims at approaching the specificities of migratory work, practices and experiences undergone by Mozambican workers on South African farms. This is a perspective that seeks to analyze and understand the legal conditions in which these workers emigrate, the nature of their employment contracts, the conditions under which they work and the possibility of sending remittances to their families in Mozambique. We relied on a qualitative approach, and through semi-structured interviews a sample of 15 Mozambican farmworkers was taken to allow us to thoroughly understand their social representations, their lived experiences on the farms as well as their everyday life. The main findings revealed that the major reasons for migrating were poverty, lack of job opportunities, family altercations, home overcrowding, food shortage due to irregular rainfall and droughts, and emulation of friends and peers. Also, individual farmers and/or farming companies hold deliberately onto informal administrative procedures in order to take advantage of unprotected and irregular migrants who cannot afford to pay a lawyer to advocate for their rights or seek support beyond their own groups. Most importantly, findings unveil that even though those workers face hardships while working on farms, their work pays off through improvements they trigger in their homes, namely through buying pieces of land where resilient houses equipped with different amenities are built, as well as stalls where small businesses take place. These facilities end up reducing the impact of poverty and fostering their relatives' quality of life and well-being.

Keywords: Undocumented emigration, Farm working Mozambicans, Lived experience, Border-crossing, Remittances.

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1. Introduction

Emigration of Mozambican workers to South Africa began in the late ninetieth century, when gold and diamond mines were discovered in that country. Since then, many Mozambicans have been looking for work in South Africa, including trade, agriculture, civil construction and other sectors, and many have been hired to work there (Muanamoha, 2008; Henrique, 2002; 2024). According to the latter author, that process reached its zenith during the twentieth century. However, by the last quarter of that century the mines decreased their hiring due to probably the incompatibilities of the political regime that emerged in Mozambique since 1975 (Marxist regime), and the dominating political regime in South Africa. Moreover, Henrique (2024) points out a few other factors that have played an important role in this decrease in hiring of Mozambican workforce such as the recruitment of more qualified workforce, and the mechanization mining procedure. In addition, we believe that other factors than those already mentioned may be the preference of local workforce to foreign and non-qualified workforce, as well as the influence of structural factors that determined the mining-commodity prices in the market.

In recent years, these circumstances have driven many who used to earn their living in mining to other sectors such as domestic work, sanitation, civil construction, farming, and other jobs that South Africans would not take. While the majority of those who migrate to South Africa and embrace these jobs do so and/or embark on that journey without any Identification Document, this study especially aimed to target those who embrace farm-working jobs.

Thus, farm workers from Gaza and Inhambane provinces were taken as the focus of this study. These provinces are located in Southern Mozambique and with some proximity to the Republic of South Africa.

The choice of these provinces relied on the fact that they are the ones which hold the largest number of Mozambican farm workers in South Africa. We believe that the geographical location of these provinces facilitates mobility of their populations to South Africa, also enhancing undocumented emigration. On the other hand, at the time of our fieldwork, Mozambican farm workers were employed on farms geographically located in Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and KwaZulu-Natal provinces in South Africa. This was so because these provinces are much closer to Mozambique and therefore, they enabled Mozambican farm workers to easily move back and forth.

Due to poverty, critical unemployment, and lack of educational opportunities in Mozambique, these workers embark on the undocumented crossing of the border that separates Mozambique from South Africa, which potentially subjects them to attack by wild animals as well as deportation by the South African authorities.

We argue that Mozambicans going to South Africa without any Identification Document and traveling in extremely dangerous conditions are susceptible to the risk of not becoming eligible for formal jobs, which might guarantee health insurance, stability at work, labor union rights, and other rights related to formal employment. Therefore, the farmers who employ them, knowing the conditions of illegality in which Mozambicans find themselves submit them to working conditions that are akin to forced labor or even slavery, with long working hours, low wages and no right to rest.

Moreover, Mozambican farm workers, despite being aware of their condition as subjugated, do not demand the restitution of rights, perhaps because they fear to be fired away by their employers, and also because they are individuals with low academic education, they are likely to be manipulated, intimidated, instrumentalized and controlled by their employers. From the outset, this perpetuates a system of exploitation of these workers, which makes them earn less income than their South African counterparts.

The relevance of this study rests on the need that we feel to contribute, through a qualitative analysis, to a thorough understanding of how the practices of migratory work on agricultural farms in South Africa are dealt with and the way in which these practices affect employment contracts, working conditions, wages, and lifestyle of those workers. The article is primarily meant to fill a gap either in literature or in fieldwork about how informal work administrative procedures affect the quality of life of those workers in terms of lack of insurance for countless risks, layoff agreements, hygiene, protection and safety at the workplace.

In addition, this article is relevant due to its intention to contribute to scientific knowledge from several perspectives. Firstly, despite the adversities that the farm-working Mozambicans face, this article aims to contribute to a social and economic approach that empirically shows how these workers improve living conditions in their country by sending remittances to their families.

Secondly, the significant progression of the study ought to invigorate scientific research related to the mobility and emigration of Mozambican farm workers, their living and

working conditions, their contributions to the improvement of their family income and other related issues.

Thus, this article addresses the following questions: What are the reasons undocumented Mozambicans migrate and engage in working on South African farms? What are the costs and benefits these undocumented Mozambicans face by migrating illegally from Mozambique to South Africa?

2. Research design

The methodological approach that guided this study is fundamentally qualitative, it provides a better understanding of motives, feelings, values, attitudes and perceptions that underline and influence behaviors as well as the context and meaning that shape lived experiences of everyday life (Ograjensek, 2016). In fact, this lens was crucial to our study as it enabled us to capture, describe and interpret the interviewees' discourses, poises, and emotions, which ended up enhancing the data collection process during our fieldwork.

The research drew on a case study method, which relied on exploratory and in-depth interviews, landscapes and pictures as sources of evidence. Gagnon (2010) by drawing on a case study, we sought to deeply understand, describe, and explain how the farm-working Mozambicans viewed, interpreted, and represented their lived experiences, namely the farm work they do, their feelings about the work itself, the worth and the meaning they attributed to the money they make, the remittances they manage to send home, the transnational ties they experience (Gagnon, 2010).

Exploratory interviews were conducted with the view to discovering relevant guidelines for the research and in order to get to the target population of this study. The interviews aimed to acquaint the interviewer with potential participants who would provide any relevant information to the research (Hughes, 2016). Thus, the interviews were basically directed at community leaders of the target communities. The option for these individuals drew on the fact that their personal experiences and daily life entitled them to provide information that could be capitalized for the research. The primary strategy consisted of identifying and interviewing one community leader for each province, nonetheless, experience in the field unveiled the fact that the chosen strategy was incompatible with the width and length of the two provinces, as well as with the dispersion of home addresses of migrants. Therefore, these phenomena resulted in three community leaders being identified and interviewed in Inhambane province, corresponding each community leader

to one of the districts as follows Homoíne, Maxixe, and Morrumbene. Likewise, in Gaza province were identified and interviewed two community leaders referring respectively to Xai-Xai and Chongoene districts.

The interviews themselves were held through talks intended to keep the interviewer knowledgeable about migration routes to South Africa, perceptions, social imaginaries and representations, remittance-sending and receiving processes, remittances management at home, migration backgrounds in the community, housing and livelihood conditions, and so forth. The resulting information was handwritten in the interviewer fieldwork diary as no recording was permitted. In the end, access to these individuals became a useful factor that enabled the interviewer to better familiarize himself with the problem, discover unknown variables, get to know some migrant's home addresses and choose the most suitable sampling method.

At all times of fieldwork, the researcher meticulously observed behaviors, homes, rituals and all aspects that could add any value to his research. By so doing, he managed to obtain empirical evidence to assess the social relevance of the problem that arises in this research.

As remarked earlier, the study took place in Inhambane and Gaza provinces respectively. Due to the territorial width of these provinces, in Inhambane province the study was located in three districts such as Homoíne, Maxixe, and Morrumbene, while in Gaza; the study took place in Chongoene and Xai-Xai districts.

To be precise, the sample comprised 15 migrants among them, 09 were interviewed in Inhambane, and 06 in Gaza. In each target district of the two provinces 03 migrants were interviewed.

Despite the importance of the role played by the community leaders during the exploratory phase of this work, they have not been included as part of the sample. Instead, they have solely been deemed to be stepping-stones through which the target participants were reached.

Thus, the sampling method was predominantly purposive, although snowball too. In the former case, participants were chosen on the basis of the information previously provided by the community leaders, whose mediation and intervention enabled the interviewer to meet participants' in-person, build trust within their group, and ultimately conduct

interviews. In the latter case, however, through migrants' social network, the interviewer was directed and introduced to new potential participants by the participants who had already been interviewed.

2.1. In-depth individual interviews

The subsequent step of this study coincided with meeting migrants and conducting interviews. At that point, the study faced a tremendous constraint. The majority of potential interviewees were not willing to cooperate with the interviewer, because they associated him with a disguised police officer trying to spy on them in order to file a lawsuit to charge them for their illegal border-crossing activities. However, the interviewer's arduous persistence in explaining to them the importance and nature of the research convinced them and led to the successful conduction of the intended interviews which resulted in the concretion of the present article. Plus, the researcher counted on the community leaders' ability to persuade migrants to participate in the study.

Thus, data collection took place in 2023 during Christmas season when most migrants return home to join their families. Subsequently, semi-structured interviews were prepared and conducted in Portuguese and later on translated into English. Prior to the beginning, interviewees were informed of the study's goals, requested their verbal or written consent, as well as assured anonymity and confidentiality of their responses.

Resorting to open-ended questions, the major discussion themes gravitated into a guideline that included migrants' sociodemographic traits, household structure, travel trajectories from Mozambique to South Africa and vice-versa, reason for migrating, wage differences between South African and foreign farm workers, remittance-sending process, working conditions, deportation experiences, transnational ties experience, and so on.

All interviews were conducted face-to-face, in a natural setting, and in the interviewees' homes, or at a location of their choice. In addition to that, field notes were taken in order to supplement the information provided by the interviewees.

Each interview session was planned to last an hour. However, to some interviewees, the interview sessions meant an opportunity to freely express their experiences, sorrows, anguishes, and frustrations in their own words. Thus, because of the critical and unanticipated manner that interviewees would put across their lived experiences, the interviewer could not help being emotionally impressed by the interviewees' narrations,

and that fact resulted in interviews lasting on average an hour and a half, and, ultimately, that approach permitted the interviewer to discover interviewees' attitudes, motivations, expectations, intentions, and preferences (Ograjensek, 2016), and contributed to laying the foundations upon which conclusions would be drawn.

The last step of this study involved an analysis of all observed and collected materials and the presentation of findings. Therefore, interviews were translated into English, read over and over again, and compared to each other for the purpose of getting rid of peripheral information and repetitions. Subsequently, to ensure ethical issues of confidentiality and anonymity related to scientific research, interviews were coded whereby pseudonymous were assigned to one and each interviewee.

3. Discussion of research findings

All data discussed here were collected through semi-structured interviews with Mozambicans who work on South Africa farms. To supplement the discussion, data from exploratory interviews were crossed and blended in the discussion.

3.1. Sociodemographic traits of interviewees

Only one out the 15 interviewees was a female. This is because men do not permit their wives to migrate alone, as cultural patterns relegate children-rearing and domestic chores to women, whereas men become breadwinners. On the other hand, on the very farms, men discourage the presence of women by besmirching and decrying them with derogatory expressions, which means women only embark on farm-working when they are single, divorced or widows, and more importantly when they do not mind sharing the same workplace with men who denigrate them.

Generally speaking, interviewees' ages varied from 19 and 46 years. The oldest ones were often those who had more skills in terms of border-crossing and life experience as a whole. All of them had come from large and extended families of more than 05 siblings and other relatives living under the same roof. Probably, this may have been a drive to poverty which hindered their parents from investing in their further education. Indeed, school attendance indicates a low level of training where 09 interviewees had only attended primary school, 04 had unsuccessfully attended secondary school, and only two of them had attended and completed secondary school.

Their household structure and number of children reveal that some of them tend to replicate their parental family structure by bearing as many children as 07, and sometimes a little less than that figure. As the majority of them were born and still live in rural areas where the economy relies primarily on agriculture, bearing many children turns out to be a welcome contribution to the much-needed future workforce for family farms.

Border-crossing trajectories disclose that 04 out of 15 migrants have been crossing the border back and forth on a regular basis and with no documents for over 10 years. In addition, other 02 have been doing the same for more than 05 years, while the remaining migrants have been embarking on that journey for 02 or less years.

Finally, as has been asserted, their residences were mostly located in rural areas, although 03 of them appeared to be in suburban ones.

3.2. Reason for migrating and border-crossing experiences

Along their discourses, interviewees offer several rationales and reasons for migrating, but before going any further, let us examine some excerpts:

I left for South Africa because my friends who had traveled previously would return with good amounts of money, clothing, as well as other goods... I wanted to be like them. So, I decided I had to leave (Daniel, 29 years old).

It was a family tragedy. My parents used to chastise me so badly, when I went to school, my colleagues bullied me in such a way that I couldn't find any serenity. So, I dropped out of school, and I left home toward South Africa. When I got there, I was hosted by some relatives that were already living in the country. So, they led me to the marketplace where I primarily sold fruits and vegetables. After a few months in the marketplace, I shifted to a new job... I mean, I went to a farm, and I worked on collecting tomatoes and potatoes (Vasco, 43 years old).

My life wasn't getting well along with my husband. He abandoned me and the children, and I needed to start my life all over again... So, I decided I was going to start by going to South Africa and making some money (Amanda, 46 years old).

As can be seen, interviewees underwent different reasons for migrating such as emulating friends and peers, mistreatment and chastisement against them at home, bullying at school, and abandonment of wife and neglect of children.

Furthermore, data reveal that certain interviewees lived far away from their schools, and as their parents could not afford to pay a bus fare on a daily basis for them to go to school, they ended up dropping out of school and heading for South Africa in order to find a job

and engage in a more rewarding life pattern. Others had wives and children depending on them, and as job offer seemed to be non-existent locally, they found their way to South African farms. Finally, there were interviewees who had been handicapped by parental neglect and abandonment, and for these reasons, they decided to leave for South Africa in unaccompanied manner and at their own risk.

For the time being, lack of financial resources to pay school fees, lack of job opportunities and the quest for solutions for immediate problems were deemed to be the most significant reasons for migrating and those reasons were considerably related to poverty, and unemployment. Despite the fact that interviewees did not mention, during his fieldwork, the researcher was able to observe significant structural reasons leading to migration such as food shortage due to irregular rainfall and/or drought, poor water supply system or lack of running water, inefficient or non-existent sanitation service, feeble housing arrangements, and home overcrowding as, on average, households encompassed extended families of more than 06 individuals.

When it comes to border-crossing experience, there are literally two main border gates separating Mozambique from South Africa, namely the Ressano Garcia and the Ponta-de-Ouro border gates. The former is always busier than the latter and as a rule, interviewees would rather opt for that border than for the latter.

Border-crossing by jumping the fence on the Ressano Garcia border entails risks such as being shot by border guards, climbing huge, and rocky hills, negotiating with smugglers in order to facilitate the journey, and sometimes bribing border guards with a view to obtaining their consent to move forward. In the meantime, the Ponta-de-Ouro border gate is located only a few kilometers away from the Maputo River which is home to crocodiles, hippopotamuses and various types of serpents. Traversing successfully the river entitles anyone to a mark of honor and courage, as many have been attacked by those animals and succumbed to death.

Bribery schemes are ubiquitous in both border gates and often encompass a network involving undocumented travelers, nearby dwellers, smugglers (hereby referred to as *marianes*), and border guards of both countries. It turns out to be a lucrative business from which nearby dwellers profit by seeking out and connecting undocumented travelers with *marianes* who then mediate a linkage between the travelers and the border guards. The narrations below unveil some of interviewees' experiences:

I spoke to a deliveryman, and I asked him to take me to South Africa. He wanted 500 Rands and then we left. Almost one kilometer away before we reached the border, I was handed to a *mariane*. Later on, we went on foot to the border fence, jumped the fence to the other side. We kept walking through the jungle and suddenly we came across two border guards. They caught us and asked us to bribe them. So, we had to give away all the money we had in the packets. After that, we moved on and finally, we reached the main road and there was the deliveryman waiting for us (Mateus, 29 years old).

As soon as we came close to the border, we found some guys whose job was to help people cross the border. Those guys are best known as *marianes*. You've got to pay them if you wish to safely cross the border. I paid 100 Rands to cross the border, and we were lucky that we didn't come across any border guard and the border-crossing was successful (Filipe, 43 years old).

I went to South Africa with a cousin. When we reached the border fence, we jumped it in and in front of us there were some border guards, but as we saw them, we set off to run, and they shot guns into the air but none of us stopped. At the same time, we were afraid of fierce animals, so we had to be silent as we escaped from the border guards. As we got to South Africa, we hid on a farm hoping to find job there, but it seemed that someone had seen us and given a call to the police and rapidly there were some police officers who apprehended us and imprisoned us for three days. Thereafter, we were deported home, but a week later I crossed the border again and I headed for Johannesburg (Abel, 39 years old).

Mateus, Filipe and Abel represent the most frequent reality undocumented Mozambican experience when moving on their way to South Africa. They often find themselves in such situations that they must endure long-distance cargo trucks or pay delivery drivers to reach the border only to cope with smugglers and corrupt border guards who dishonestly profit from them.

More precisely, this approach ends up perpetuating a bribery-based public service that ultimately weakens the border protection system and generates an unfair accumulation of money for the benefit of a network that comprises nearby dwellers, smugglers, and border guards.

Conversely, those who like Abel and his cousin are not willing to deal with smugglers or bribe border guards, they risk being killed with gunshots or being apprehended, imprisoned and deported at once. From that point of view, immersing in bribery schemes turns out to be less onerous to undocumented Mozambicans since by so doing they avoid apprehension, imprisonment, and deportation. Furthermore, they manage to avoid apprehension at any cost as it ends up causing financial, physical or emotional losses. For instance, those who face apprehension may be deported, and deportation, in turn, leads to their embarrassment and shame upon arrival at home as they may lose some of their

belongs along the way, and arrive at home empty-handedly, and sometimes carrying debts and bills to pay.

For the above reasons, deportees tend to return to South Africa immediately before they are able to reach their homes. In fact, with regard to these scenarios, some interviewees asserted that working on farms rendered them more safety than working as janitors, street-vendors, in civil construction or in any other urban job. Farming happens to take place in the countryside where seldom are there police, or immigration officers watching, or asking questions. In addition, the countryside is a landscape that offers places to hide and gives some sense of safety. On the contrary, cities and urban areas are often surrounded by government officials who may ask for migratory status from anyone, eventually leading to the apprehension of those whose migratory statuses happen to be irregular.

To some interviewees, making their moves along with as many undocumented migrants as possible empowers them to navigate through negotiations with either smugglers or border guards in order to lower the amount of money to be charged for their border-crossing. Hence, as soon as they pay the agreed amount, they are all set to sabotage the border fence by climbing in it under the border guards' connivence at any given time.

Beyond the point where they climb the border fence, switching off their cellphones and keeping quiet while marching through huge trees, uneven hills and amorphous rocks will prevent them from being caught by different groups of border guards on patrol who, in turn, might demand new bribery on their own behalf.

Once on the farms, some of those who happen to go for the first time may be lucky to immediately find a job. However, others may navigate through a jobless status for as long as five months or more. At that point, begging or depending on the goodwill of others appears to be temporary options that lift them out of their distress. In accordance with one of the interviewees, the major reasons why one may be jobless for such a long time are related to cultural and linguistic barriers, and as some Mozambicans are not familiarized with South African traditional customs nor are they capable of speaking English language or other local languages, they often find themselves facing joblessness for quite a long time.

In sum, data show that the most outstanding reasons for migrating are emulation of friends and peers, poverty, lack of job opportunities, family altercations, home overcrowding, and desire to live a better life standard. Aside from these reasons, observation during fieldwork

indicated climate-related issues such as droughts and irregular rainfall as migrating drivers. Likewise, data point out that border-crossing experience entails fundamentally bribery schemes which benefit local dwellers, smugglers and border guards of both Mozambique and South Africa.

4.3. Salary differences among South African and Mozambican farm workers

According to some interviewees, there are no differences in terms of salaries or any other criteria. All farm workers are treated equally regardless of their nationality, ethnicity or creed. Nonetheless, not all interviewees share this depiction. In effect, the assertions below are to a great extent self-explanatory at that point:

In my workplace, we are all foreigners. Sometimes, South African bosses prefer foreign workers to South African ones because that refrains them from paying additional benefits to their workers (Manuel, 22 years old).

When you are an illegal guy, your boss tells you that you are going to make a certain amount of money, but at the end of the month, they pay you less than that, and you have nowhere to complain. To make matters worse, the least mistake you make, they admonish you so badly [...], they yell at you, and then they fire you without any benefits... just like a dog (Jaime, 19 years old).

The interviewees' rhetoric indicates that farmer employers are more favorable to foreign farm workers than to South African ones not for the sake of merely being generous to the former ones, but rather because those farmers can freely exploit them, pay less money to them or pay no money at all, and inflict upon them overtime work without any additional payment. As these farm workers do not hold documents, they cannot open a bank account, thereby their salaries are handed over to them in cash. Thus, according to one of interviewees, when the day for payment comes, some farmers call the immigration officers and inform them about a presence of undocumented foreign people on the farm. By doing so, farmers manage to get away with their duty to pay salaries, since the foreign farm workers will then have to be deported.

Mozambican farm workers are relentlessly submitted to such an exploitation system without being able to complain or bring a lawsuit against the farmers because their irregular migratory status weakens the intention to do so. Moreover, any complaint or lawsuit would result in their immediate expulsion from the workplace, and eventually other intimidation patterns such as beating and mobbing.

Due to the fear of deportation, Mozambican farm workers subject themselves to subjugation, manipulation, instrumentalization, silence, conformism, blackmail, and these attitudes deter them from making as much money as their South African counterparts, and ultimately lead them to subservience, docility and servility. Paradoxically, these attitudes generate from the bottom of the hearts of South African farm workers sentiments of hatred, jealousy and xenophobia towards Mozambicans who happen to be accused of taking South African people's jobs, women and everything else. The excerpt below calls for an accurate attention to that:

We are not welcome to South Africa. They say that we take their jobs, their women, and the whole thing. So, salaries are paid in a discriminatory manner, and there is some sort of mistreatment against Mozambican farm workers (Fernando, 19 years old).

By being able to submit themselves to extremely demanding working conditions in exchange for less payment, Mozambican farm workers are viewed derogatorily by their South African counterparts as those who drive salaries to low standards, and for that reason Mozambican farm worker become unwanted and undesirable to their South African coworkers.

Thus, sometimes Mozambican farm workers suffer from insults, moral offenses, and slanders. Despite those provocative behaviors, they prevent themselves from riots or clashes because they believe that South African authorities always act partially in favor of local citizens, whereas foreigners are blamed and left unprotected.

In summary, there are substantially more differences than similarities in treatment of both South African and Mozambican farm workers. In accordance with interviewees, South Africans have other benefits than salary, their salary is determined on the basis of a national minimum wage pattern, their working hours are defined under the law, and any overtime work is susceptible to supplementary payment. On the contrary, any irregular farm workers, Mozambicans included, are subject to arbitrary working conditions and wages, as well as unhuman treatment such as insults, humiliations, slanders, and intimidations.

4.4. Working conditions

On the whole, interviewees describe their working conditions as arduous, harsh, and extremely demanding long working hours, most frequently beginning from early in the

morning and with no specific ending hour. Despite that, no overtime work is paid, no talking with coworkers is allowed, let alone resting, or eating a snack.

For the time being, as they leave the farm by the end of the day, resorting to an alcoholic beverage appears to be an antidote that alleviates their exhaustion and depletion, as indicated in the following quote:

My job is pretty arduous. We start the journey around 07 in the morning and there is no ending time. You know, that is what modern slavery is about [...]. I mean, we don't even have a snack to eat, and sometimes when we are done, we end up running to a bar to get some booze and drink to forget our sorrow (Vasco, 43 years old).

When it comes to hygiene, protection and safety, some farmers provide their farm workers with boots, gloves, uniform, and depending on each case, masks and helmets are provided too. However, none of these privileges is afforded to irregular farm workers in favor of whom there is no concern for safety. With regard to it, Fernando remarks:

[...] there is no concern for work safety, and when we ask for these things [work gear], the boss responds to us in such a rude way and says that each one of us is responsible for himself (Fernando, 19 years old).

Broadly speaking, and with respect to undocumented farm workers, working conditions on farms do not hold onto the labor law, and therefore farm workers are easily submitted to endless working hours, with no right to annual leave, no parental leave, no sick pay, no holiday pay, no written employment contract agreement, and no additional benefit other than paycheck.

Aside from not benefiting from work insurance, their individual farmers or their farming companies do not cover medical expenses for work accidents and while on recovery, no benefit is granted to them, which means the individual farmers, or the farming companies only pay for the work already performed. Moreover, even when injured in a work accident, or afflicted by any disease, they do not make an attempt to go the hospital as they believe nurses and physicians manage to report their presence in the hospital to the immigration officers. Here is what Amanda affirms at this point:

We don't have insurance and live an indigent life. We don't even have where to live and are exposed to heat, cold and other climate events [...]. When we are sick, we never go to any hospital [...], we fear that the hospital personnel may call the police to deport us (Amanda, 46 years old).

Some interviewees regularly suffer from money deductions from their paychecks allegedly with a view to funding their future retirement pensions. But being irregular migrants

generates distrust and uncertainty among farm workers who view themselves as victims of premeditated deceit.

A couple of discounts are deducted from us, but I seriously don't see any benefits. They say the money being deducted is going to be returned in terms of future pensions, but I think they are deceiving us (Florindo, 32 years old).

That sentiment of deceit is reinforced by their clandestinity status and the assumption that by being irregular migrants, they are not supposed to remain in the country, and thereby their deportation may inadvertently occur at any given moment.

So far, in their workplace, all administrative procedures are informally dealt with, and unclear and arbitrary decisions are made only to relegate their fate to the mercy of the employer's free will. Consequently, those farm workers are not permitted to affiliate or join any formally organized associations of workers as labor unions. Moreover, collective negotiation, mediation or arbitration are unthinkable, and attempts to complain about any unfair treatment result in work dismissal.

Despite their fear of intimidation and work dismissal, farm workers are so committed to earning their living that they cannot devote their time to thoroughly reflecting on their own human dignity, as stated below:

We're striving to win everyday bread [...]. How are we going to waste our time thinking about such a thing as labor union? (Mateus, 29 years old).

Data indicated that interviewees had low schooling. In fact, only two out of 15 had successfully attended secondary school to the end. Perhaps, this may be a reason that hinders them from raising awareness about the precarious working conditions they are engaged in, fighting for their human rights, and developing a comprehensive understanding of a labor union as well as its importance for the betterment of workers' professional well-being.

Taking into account these fragile and unprotected working conditions, the availability of a legal representative or a lawyer would be crucial to advocate for their labor rights. Nevertheless, they cannot afford to pay a lawyer, nor can they hold accountable anyone who infringes their human rights as their lives are limited to the farms where they work and live while often comparing them to prisons.

Despite not being permitted to join any labor union, and not being able to afford to pay for legal assistance through a lawyer, Mozambican farmworkers manage to defend each other

whenever possible. For instance, when a fellow coworker is afflicted by an illness and cannot work, they do his work to prevent him from being dismissed or fired. In order to survive as a group, this is one of the strategies through which they protect and come to the aid of each other.

In sum, interviewees refer to their working conditions as arduous, harsh and demanding, whereas no overtime work is paid. Furthermore, they do not benefit from any work gear such as uniforms, boots, gloves, and most of their rights are obliterated. In addition to that, they are not allowed to join any labor union, and that weakens both their labor and human rights, and demands advocacy for protecting and dignifying their lives.

4.5. Salaries and remittances

On average, Mozambican farm workers earn a monthly salary of 2,465 South African Rands which is roughly equivalent to USD \$136. 98. Despite making as little money as the figure above, they are able to save as much as possible in order to meet their everyday needs and remit home either in cash, foodstuff or other goods.

Due to their undocumented status, they could not and still cannot remit money through formal channels (Bank Wire Transfer, Western Union, and/or Money Gram). This meant they had to keep their money on their own and take it home when they were able to travel during Christmas season. Otherwise, they had to hand the money to a delivery driver who might eventually run as many risks as assaults along the way, or even take the money for himself and ultimately pretend and/or simulate an assault.

In recent years, a surge of small remitting agencies has been enabling safe remitting, despite high fees remitters are charged. Furthermore, remitters can also count on cellphone remitting procedures, which appear to be instantaneous, affordable and safe.

The great majority of Mozambican farm workers remit on a regular basis using these channels while others do so not so frequently. The amounts are often as small as 1000 South African Rands (roughly USD\$55.5) and sometimes less than this figure. The recipients spent remittances on buying pieces of land for building more resilient and bigger houses, and stalls where small businesses are conducted. In addition, remittances fund school fees, medications, weddings, potlucks, and everyday necessities. Fernando and Jaime, who remit on a monthly basis, state their experience as follows:

I always send money home, and I am planning to build my house with that money. I send 1000 Rands and I keep the remaining amount for my expenses (Fernando, 19 years old).

I send home some 900 Rands monthly to help my mommy and brothers, and I have to keep with me some money for my daily expenditures (Jaime, 19 years old).

Although the lived experiences on the farms are filled by hardships, distresses, and exhaustions, they turn out to pay off through the improvements Mozambican farmworkers manage to trigger in their homes. In effect, prior to embarking on their farmjobs, their houses were made of flimsy and feeble material, unable to resist heavy rain and winds, mostly tiny houses, with no windows, no balconies, no electricity, and no running water, let alone restrooms, and kitchens on the inside.

On the contrary, the houses they built during the time they had been remitting money unveil a more resilient condition when compared to the previous ones. Facades display large balconies, several windows, presence of rooms and other compartments, as well as amenities such as electricity and running water.

It is worth mentioning that aside from money, these farm workers also remit other resources and goods to their kins and acquaintances back home, such as sugar, milk, eggs, lotion, clothing, soap, cooking oil, potatoes, schoolbooks, beds, blankets, microwaves, stoves, and so forth. In general, these goods are bought in South Africa and shipped to Mozambique where they allow the beneficiary families to improve their standard of living and to enhance their well-being.

In sum, data indicates that interviewees are unable to remit resorting to Bank Wire Transfer, and most of their money is remitted either using small remitting agencies or cellphone remitting procedures. Money is remitted on a regular basis in small but meaningful amounts that serve well to meet the recipient's everyday needs. On the other hand, data unveils that other than money, interviewees remit foodstuff, clothing and different goods whose sum and substance end up improving the recipient's quality of life and well-being.

3.6. Satisfaction

In spite of all hardships and distresses interviewees face on farms, some of them express their satisfaction with their work as it lifts them out of unemployment, makes them earn money, send remittances home and improve their relatives' standard of living. Other

sources of satisfaction stem from their ability to learn how to speak English, to meet new people and build different capacities.

Nonetheless, other interviewees do not agree with the foregoing assertions. Instead, low and unstable salaries, long working hours, abusive treatment as well as lack of respect frequently lead to their dissatisfaction. Likewise, sometimes agriculture work demands that some workers cope with chemical and toxic substances such as fertilizers, and pesticides whose handlers must rely on masks, gloves, special eyeglasses, and uniforms in order to protect themselves from skin irritation, poisoning and/or intoxication. From the interviewees' perspectives, those work gears ought to be provided by the employer, but they are currently not being provided at all, and Mozambican farm workers must cope with such substances in an unprotected manner. Otherwise, they must provide them for themselves.

In the main, interviewees depict themselves as modern slaves who risk their health in exchange for limited rewards. With regard to this, Daniel proclaims as follows:

How am I supposed to be satisfied with the job? It's like slavery [...], and the boss doesn't care about our safety. Besides, salaries don't pay off (Daniel, 29 years old).

On account of these tribulations, interviewees find no time to dedicate to themselves, or to hang out with their acquaintances. In their opinion, no one deserves to live like they do, and they also believe their work brings about no future, no personal development, or growth at all. To make matters worse, their irregular migratory status compels them all the time to be on the alert with no inner peace. Moreover, they consider that the only thing that matters to their employers is profiting from them, therefore, it is not worth recommending anyone engage in the work they do.

Things have moved the other way around in South Africa. They now manage to formally hire South African people only [...] most Mozambicans who are still there, they are grieving, but they are not courageous enough to return home, because they are ashamed to return the way they left (Mateus, 29 years old).

In order to surmount their adversities at the workplace, interviewees admit that some improvements ought to be carried out, mainly through provision of written employment contact, humanization of treatment of all workers, increase in salaries, investment in safe working conditions, avoidance of salary delays, overtime work payment, and so on. Interviewees consider that working on improving these aspects would generate

satisfaction, foster productivity, enhance motivation and ultimately incentivize their farmers' revenues.

In short, interviewees express extremely divergent viewpoints regarding the extent to which they are satisfied with their work. Some say they are satisfied with it as it lifts them out of unemployment, while also allowing them to make money and send remittances homewards. Others, instead, refer to dissatisfaction with their work because of long working hours, abusive treatment, low wages, lack of personal development, and professional growth. When surmounted these constraints, interviewees believe that their employers would increase revenues, workers would foster productivity, as well as enhance motivation and satisfaction.

5. Conclusion

The starting point of this research has been marked by two questions, namely: "What are the reasons undocumented Mozambicans migrate and engage in working on South African farms? What are the costs and benefits these undocumented Mozambicans face by migrating from Mozambique to South Africa?".

In order to respond to these questions, we embarked primarily on literature review by which we became knowledgeable about critical concepts such as forced migration, economic migration, remittances, and so many more. These concepts have been crucial to the present research as they helped shape the research structure, while also laying the foundation upon which data collection was conducted and conclusions were drawn.

The subsequent step dealt with data analysis whose sum and substance led to the following conclusions: cultural patterns of the target population relegate children-rearing and domestic chores to women. On the other hand, men working on farms deter women from engaging in that work by denigrating and besmirching them with depreciative and derogatory words. Thus, in the face of these reasons, women engage in farm-working employment when they are single, divorced, or widows. Otherwise, they do so when they are able to endure all slander and defamation coming from their male fellows.

The majority of interviewees came from large extended families, where their parents were unable to invest in their schooling due mainly to poverty. Therefore, they had to start early crossing the Mozambican-South African border in the quest for a more rewarding standard

of living, whereas some of them had been doing so within more than 10 years without any documents.

There are two main border-crossing gates, namely the Ressano Garcia (In South Africa referred to as “Lebombo Border Post”), and the Ponta-de-Ouro one (Known in South Africa as “Kosi Bay Border Post”). From data, it has been inferred that crossing these borders irregularly offers several risks such as attacks by wild animals, gunshots by border guards, coping with smugglers, bribing corrupt border guards of both countries and climbing rocky and uneven hills.

Corruption and bribery enabled undocumented Mozambicans to jump the border fence at any time under the border guards’ consent. On the contrary, those who made any attempt to jump the fence without bribing the border guards became victims of gunshots, apprehension, imprisonment, and deportation.

With regard to that, the present study found that undocumented Mozambican did their best to avoid being deported, because deportation led to embarrassment and shame upon arrival at home. In fact, within the theoretical framework, it has been corroborated that economic migrants are expected to bring financial benefits (Nisrane, 2019; Setrana, & Kleist, 2022), and returning home because of deportation generates a burden of shame and humiliation (Andersson, 2014), as some migrants take loans from their communities and invest in their journeys in expectation of remittances (Carr, 2016). This means that when these expectations fall short on account of deportation, migrants and their relatives experience tremendous frustration and disappointment. Thus, these were some of the reasons why undocumented Mozambicans remarked that they preferred working on farms to urban jobs, as farms offered several hiding places which permitted them to escape from deportation.

According to Msabah (2022), migration has taken place over all human existence and its intensity reveals the deep desire for freedom as well as an urgent need for a dignified future. On the other hand, a study conducted by Kefale & Mohammed (2015) found that the main drivers for youth migration were unemployment, poverty, family and peer pressure, shortage of arable land in rural areas, limited development of industrial and service sectors in urban areas, and inducement by smugglers and traffickers. Another study pointed out other drivers such as lack of livelihood opportunities, lack of basic recreational facilities and absence of services like water and electricity supply (Kahsay,

2019). Likewise, the present article reiterates some of those findings. Thus, the major reasons for migrating were based on poverty, lack of job opportunities, family altercations, home overcrowding, food shortage due to irregular rainfall and droughts, and emulation of friends and peers. These reasons were often reinforced by some other significant structural reasons such as lack of running water, inefficient or non-existent sanitation service, and flimsy housing arrangements.

The irregular migratory status that Mozambican farm workers faced turned them into an easy target to exploit, to pay less money, to inflict overtime work upon without a supplementary payment, to manipulate, and to instrumentalize. Despite these predicaments, fear of expulsion and/or deportation drove them to subservience, docility and servility. Thus, from this statement, we conclude that for the same work, same professional category and same work schedule, Mozambican farm workers were paid less money, although submitted to more work pressure than their South African coworkers, and these factors reinforced abusive treatment like insults, slanders, intimidations and humiliations against Mozambican farm workers.

Working conditions on farms have been described as arduous, harsh, and with an undetermined ending hour. Furthermore, protection and safety at the workplace come only to South African farm workers who are then provided with boots, gloves, uniform and other work gears. Conversely, work gears are not granted to undocumented Mozambican. Moreover, their farming companies and/or individual farmers do not cover medical expenses for work accident, nor do they allow their foreign undocumented workers to join a labor union in order to protect their labor rights. In addition to that, undocumented Mozambican go regularly through money deduction from their monthly salaries supposedly for financing their retirement pensions. Hence, taking into account these facts, we draw the conclusion that farming companies and/or individual farmers hold deliberately onto informal administrative procedures in order to take advantage of unprotected and irregular migrants who, in turn, cannot afford to pay a lawyer to advocate for their rights, nor can they seek support beyond their own groups.

When it comes to remittances, Mozambican farm workers do not resort to Bank Wire Transfer, Western Union, and MoneyGram. Rather, they remit using small remitting agencies or cellphone remitting procedures. Their remittances are not limited to money but also include goods such as stoves, microwaves, foodstuff, clothing, schoolbooks, and so forth. Given these facts, we conclude that even though Mozambican farm workers face

hardships, depletion, and mistreatment while working on farms, their work pays off through improvements they trigger in their homes, namely reducing the impact of poverty through buying pieces of land where resilient houses equipped with different amenities are built, as well as stalls where small businesses take place. Thus, these facilities end up enhancing their relatives' quality of life and well-being.

Satisfaction emerged as a divergent category in the farm workers' experiences as some admitted they were satisfied with their work, while other pointed out they were not satisfied at all. The former justified their satisfaction with the fact of being employed, which allowed them to make money, send remittances home, and improve their lives. The latter, instead, referred to their dissatisfaction due to long working hours, abusive treatment at the workplace, low wages, and lack of professional and personal development and growth. Thus, as a way to surmount these problems, they recommended a provision of written employment contract, increase of salaries, investment in safe working conditions, and so on. As far as Mozambican workers were concerned, these recommendations aimed at fostering productivity, enhancing motivation, and incentivizing the farmers' revenues.

In sum, from the foregoing description, we draw to the conclusion that Mozambican farm workers fall into the category of economic migrants who have voluntarily been migrating to that South Africa due fundamentally to economic reasons (Castles, 2005). The sum and substance of all these conclusions have allowed us to meet our research goals and respond to our research questions. It is worth reiterating that all data collection process took place in Mozambique and included a small sample of 15 Mozambican who work on South African farms. Thus, in order to attain more comprehensive and significant findings, a recommendation for future research points out that researchers manage to traverse the Mozambican-South African border and reach South African farms with a view to observing in-person Mozambicans' lived experiences. Doing so would add priceless value to their approaches. Future researchers ought also to broaden their sample to be able to rely on more diverse lived experiences as well as sources of information.

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